

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D4.4 - Meta-analysis of splicing and expression QTLs across three cohorts

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1. Executive Summary

The aim of the CINECA project is to develop common infrastructure to support federated data analysis across national cohorts in Europe, Canada and Africa. This involved federated data discovery (work package 1), authorisation and authentication infrastructure (work package 2), metadata harmonisation (work package 3), federated analysis applications (work packages 4 and 5) and ethical and legal framework (work package 6). In this deliverable, we report on the progress that we have made over the past four years to streamline the federated genetic analysis of molecular traits across multiple international cohorts.

The previous state of the art for federated genetic analysis of molecular traits is exemplified by the approach taken by the eQTLGen consortium¹, which relied on manual installation of software dependencies, manual execution of complex analysis steps, and sharing of large summary files between cohorts. Inspired by these limitations, we have designed and implemented six modular workflows to quantify and normalise molecular traits (such as gene expression or RNA splicing levels) from sequencing data (workflows 1-2), pre-process genotype data (workflow 3) and test for associations between molecular traits and genotypes (workflows 4-6). Our approach improves on the previous state of the art by packaging software dependencies into Docker/Singularity containers, using the Nextflow language to orchestrate complex multi-step workflows, and using the HASE(1) framework to significantly reduce the amount of data that need to be transferred between cohorts.

To encourage the adoption and re-use of our workflows by third parties, we have developed comprehensive training materials and prepared realistic open access datasets to test execution in diverse compute infrastructures. Finally, we demonstrate how our workflows can be used to perform federated analysis across multiple real cohorts located in Switzerland, Germany, the Netherlands and Estonia.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached the following objectives:

- a) Develop modular and reproducible workflows for genetic analysis of molecular traits.
- b) Assemble realistic open access datasets to support testing and deployment of workflows on novel computation infrastructures.
- c) Demonstrate federated analysis of molecular traits using real-world datasets hosted in multiple distributed locations.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

In [Deliverable 4.1](#)² we identified four levels of data access. These were:

¹ <https://github.com/molgenis/systemsgenetics/wiki/eQTL-mapping-analysis-cookbook-%28eQTLGen%29>

² <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1VIPo8ebS0nCjszn1Hhnh3QfGba2t3z5V4yX1UZcyHyE/edit>

- Level 1: Open access.
- Level 2: Controlled access with download (e.g. via EGA).
- Level 3: Controlled access without download.
- Level 4: No access to individual-level data.

Over the past three years, we have seen an increasing shift towards levels 3 and 4 of data access. As an example of Level 3, instead of moving large datasets between institutions and continents to perform analysis, datasets are increasingly being made available within Trusted Research Environments (TRE) where analysis is performed locally either on public or private clouds (2). The ‘no download’ policy is typically further enforced by the requirement that all results intended to be exported from the TRE need to be manually reviewed to ensure that no individual-level data is exported. This approach has now been adopted by multiple large national biobanks such as the UK Biobank’s [Research Analysis Platform](#)³ (RAP), FinnGen, [Danish National Genome Center](#)⁴, [Our Future Health](#)⁵, [Genomics England](#)⁶ and All of Us Research.

The shift towards stricter data sharing models is driven by three main reasons:

1. It increases data security by eliminating the possibility that there could be unauthorised copies of the data in different locations.
2. It makes it possible to verify that the data are used only for intended purposes (e.g. via logging) and only authorised summary-level results are exported from the TRE (e.g. via manual review).
3. It reduces data transfer costs and time by removing the need to move large datasets between data centres.

In contrast, in recommendations adopted on 18 June 2021⁷, European Data Protection Board has concluded that remote access to individual-level data from a third country in a cloud environment (e.g. a TRE) is considered to be equivalent to data transfer to said country under GDPR. This interpretation is also adopted by the Estonian Biobank. As a result, it is not always possible to grant access to individual-level genotype data even if the data is stored in a secure cloud environment. Furthermore, some smaller cohorts might not always be able to set up their own TREs, but they might have similar legal obligations to ensure data security and prevent use for unintended purposes. In this setting, alternative arrangements are needed that enable data analysis without access to individual level data (Level 4). This is typically achieved via ‘manual federation’ where a local analyst in control of the data executes the analysis workflow and reports back summary-level results (Figure 1).

³ <https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/enable-your-research/research-analysis-platform>

⁴ <https://ngc.dk/forskning-og-internationalt-samarbejde/ngc-forsknerservice/hvordan-soeger-du-om-adgang>

⁵

<https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20220912005289/en/DNAexus-Selected-as-Platform-Provider-of-the-Trusted-Research-Environment-for-UK%E2%80%99s-Largest-Health-Research-Program>

⁶ <https://www.genomicsengland.co.uk/news/research-environment-covid-19-lifebit-aws>

⁷ Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data. Version 2.0. Adopted on 18 June 2021

https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-06/edpb_recommendations_202001vo.2.0_supplementarymeasure_transferstools_en.pdf

Regardless of the mode of federation chosen (manual or TRE) it is essential to reduce the effort required to repeat the same analysis on different compute infrastructures. This is especially important for molecular traits that often require computationally intensive processing steps such as read alignment, genotype imputation or association testing that require large-scale parallel processing. A powerful way to achieve this is to implement the data analysis steps as a reproducible workflow in one of the broadly supported workflow languages (e.g. Nextflow, WDL or CWL) and package all of the software dependencies as Docker or Singularity containers. In CINECA WP4 we have chosen the Nextflow system, which is now broadly supported on both academic High Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructures as well as on commercial cloud environments⁸.

Manual federation

- **Step 1:** Code is sent to a **local analyst** at each location.
- **Step 2:** **Local analyst** performs the analysis, validates the results and sends back to a central location controlled by the **researcher**.
- **Step 3:** **Researcher** combines the results from multiple locations in a meta-analysis framework.

Trusted Research Environment (TRE)

- **Step 0:** **Researcher** obtains legal permission to view individual-level data (data access agreement).
- **Step 1:** **Researcher** performs the analysis within the secure environment of the TRE.
- **Step 2:** **Researcher** asks for permission to export the results; results are reviewed by the **local analyst** to ensure that no individual-level data is exported.
- **Step 3:** **Researcher** combines the results from multiple locations in a meta-analysis framework.

Figure 1. Two main frameworks for performing large-scale federated analysis across multiple cohorts.

In this deliverable, we will first give an overview of six modular Nextflow workflows we have developed to support federated analysis of molecular QTLs. Next, we demonstrate how these workflows can be deployed and tested on different infrastructures using training materials and open access datasets. Finally, we present two use cases where we have used these workflows to perform federated eQTL analysis across multiple real-world cohorts located in Switzerland, Germany, the Netherlands and Estonia.

3.2 Description of Work

Overview of the workflows

We have developed six modular and containerised workflows for federated analysis of molecular traits. These workflows cover gene expression and splicing quantification (eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq), molecular trait normalisation and quality control (eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm), genotype imputation (eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute), *cis*-QTL association testing and fine mapping (eQTL-Catalogue/qtmap), data encoding workflow for *trans*-QTL association testing ([eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations](https://github.com/eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations)⁹), and *trans*-QTL meta-analysis ([eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis](https://github.com/eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis)¹⁰).

⁸ <https://www.nextflow.io/docs/latest/executor.html#>

⁹ <https://github.com/eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis>

All six workflows follow the same general patterns:

- Workflows are written in the Nextflow language.
- All software dependencies have been packaged into publicly available Docker/Singularity containers available from quay.io¹¹.
- All workflows come with small test datasets to simplify deployment on new infrastructures.

The six workflows are:

1. Gene expression and splicing quantification

The [eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq](https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq)¹² workflow (Figure 2) is inspired by the nf-core/rnaseq workflow and performs adapter trimming (TrimGalore), alignment to the reference genome (HISAT2 (3)), gene and exon-level read counting (featureCounts (4)), read coverage visualisation (deepTools (5)), genotype concordance checks (qtltools MBV (6)), splice junction quantification (LeafCutter (7)) and transcript expression quantification (Salmon, txrevise). The correctly formatted reference annotations are available from the eQTL Catalogue FTP server¹³.

Figure 2. Overview of the eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq workflow.

2. Molecular trait normalisation and quality control

After molecular traits (such as gene expression and splicing) have been quantified, they need to be appropriately quality controlled and normalised to support association testing with linear regression. These steps are implemented in the [eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm](https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm)¹⁴ workflow that takes raw results from the rnaseq workflow and applies appropriate normalisation techniques for each quantification method. Gene and exon counts are quantile normalised using the `cqn` (8) R package before inverse normal transformation is applied. In contrast, transcript and splice-junction quantification results are converted into proportional estimates before inverse normal transformation is applied. The workflow also produces a QC report in html format, which contains the principal component analysis (PCA) and multidimensional

¹¹ <https://quay.io/user/eqtlcatalogue>; <https://quay.io/organization/eqtlgen>

¹² <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq>

¹³ http://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/spot/eQTL/references/rnaseq_complete_reference_290322.tar.gz

¹⁴ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm>

scaling (MDS) plots of the gene expression data as well as concordance checks for biological sex and genotype data.

3. Genotype imputation and quality control

The [eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute](#)¹⁵ workflow (Figure 3) takes raw genotype data in plink format¹⁶, lifts variant positions to the correct reference genome version with CrossMap (9), aligns the genotypes to the reference panel with Genotype Harmonizer (10), performs QC filtering with bcftools, phases the genotypes with Eagle (11) and finally imputes the genotypes with Minimac4 (12). The workflow also correctly handles the genotypes on the X chromosome, performing imputation separately for the pseudoautosomal regions (PAR) and the non-PAR regions. The correctly formatted 1000 Genomes 30x on GRCh38 reference panel (13) files are available from the eQTL Catalogue FTP server¹⁷.

Figure 3. Overview of the eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute workflow.

4. *cis*-QTL association testing

The [eQTL-Catalogue/qtlmap](#)¹⁸ workflow (Figure 4) takes normalised molecular trait matrix along with metadata from the qcnorm workflow and imputed genotypes from the genimpute workflow and uses the fastQTL (14) tool to test for association between genetic variants located near each molecular trait (e.g. +/- 1Mb around the gene) and the normalised trait value. These associations are referred to *cis* quantitative trait loci (*cis*-QTLs). To account for unmeasured confounders and population structure, the workflow also calculates principal components of the trait and genotype matrices and includes those as covariates in the linear model. Finally, the workflow also performs statistical fine mapping using the susieR (15) software. The summary results created by the qtlmap workflow do not contain any individual-level data and follow the formatting conventions of the eQTL Catalogue (16), making it easy to integrate new datasets with the existing ones available from the eQTL Catalogue.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute/>

¹⁶ <https://www.cog-genomics.org/plink/1.9/input#bed>

¹⁷ http://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/spot/eQTL/references/genimpute_complete_reference_150322.tar.gz

¹⁸ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/qtlmap/>

Figure 4. Overview of the eQTL-Catalogue/qtmap workflow.

5. Trans-eQTL encoding workflow

The *trans*-eQTL encoding workflow ([eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations](https://github.com/eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations)¹⁹) uses the HASE (1) framework to encode individual-level gene expression and genotype data prior to transferring the data to a central site. Classical meta-analyses in multi-cohort settings rely on performing within cohort analyses at the cohorts site, subsequently transferring the outcomes to a central site, and finally, performing a meta-analysis at this central site. This results in very large amounts of data for each cohort (~4Tb). These large amounts of data are technically very challenging to share and store for meta-analysis. In contrast, the HASE methodology functions by performing all intensive analyses at the central site. HASE calculates derivatives from the input genotype and phenotype data. This results in encoded and derived matrices in which the linear relatedness of input data is maintained, and personal level data is absent. This approach makes it technically feasible to perform very large-scale *trans*-eQTL analyses.

The *trans*-eQTL encoding workflow is performed per cohort. In this workflow, genotype data is converted to HDF5 format, which is the accepted format of HASE. Then, the genotype and phenotype data of interest are encoded into two output matrices in a harmonised manner, and using covariate data, partial derivatives are calculated. This is the minimum amount of data that is required for the central meta-analysis to ultimately determine full *trans*-eQTL results.

6. Trans-eQTL meta-analysis workflow

The *trans*-eQTL meta-analysis workflow ([eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis](https://github.com/eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis)²⁰) combines and analyses the data shared by individual cohorts prepared by the *trans*-eQTL encoding workflow. Initially, cohort data is merged. Then, following our adapted HASE methodology, per-cohort analyses

¹⁹ <https://github.com/eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations>

²⁰ <https://github.com/eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis>

are performed, allowing us to apply per-cohort filtering and confounder adjustment. To account for likely heterogeneity between studies, we perform an inverse variance meta-analysis on all cohort-specific results. The per-cohort analyses and the combined meta-analyses are performed in separate steps and chunks, which are parallelized over. The results are saved in a storage-efficient parquet format²¹.

Modular design, open access datasets and tutorials

We have deliberately designed the workflows to be modular so that different workflows could be combined to achieve different data analysis objectives. A few potential scenarios have been highlighted on Figure 5.

Figure 5. Schematic of how the developed workflows can be combined to achieve different analysis tasks.

Open access datasets

Before federated data analysis can be performed on real, private data it is important to verify that the workflows work as intended on new compute infrastructures either in manual federation or TRE setting (Figure 1). This is best achieved by using well-documented synthetic or open access datasets of realistic size and complexity. In the CINECA project, we have set up multiple such datasets to

²¹ <https://parquet.apache.org/docs/>

support diverse use cases²². Below we describe two open access datasets that we have prepared to support the testing and development of gene expressions and splicing QTL analysis workflows.

CEDAR. We downloaded raw gene expression and genotype data from the CEDAR cohort (17) from ArrayExpress (accessions [E-MTAB-6666](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress/studies/E-MTAB-6666)²³ and [E-MTAB-6667](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress/studies/E-MTAB-6667)²⁴). We called genotypes using Illumina's proprietary GenomeStudio software and converted the genotype calls into plink format. We performed genotype imputation using the eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute workflow. We also extracted raw gene expression microarray intensity values from the submitted .idat files and normalised the data with the eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm workflow. The raw and processed genotype and gene expression data together with harmonised sample metadata are available from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6171348>. These files can be used as realistic examples to test the eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute, eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm and eQTL-Catalogue/qtmap workflows on new compute infrastructures.

GEUVADIS. The RNA-seq data from the GEUVADIS project (18) is freely available from the European Nucleotide Archive (accession [PRJEB3366](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB3366)²⁵). The genotype data can be downloaded from the FTP server of the [1000 Genomes Project](https://www.1000genomes.org/)²⁶. To facilitate the development of end-to-end workflows from data discovery (CINECA WP1), authentication and authorisation (CINECA WP2) and federated analysis (WP4), we have also made the GEUVADIS RNA-seq fastq files and whole genome sequencing genotype calls available via the [CINECA synthetic cohort EUROPE UK1](https://www.cineca-project.eu/synthetic-data/scd-europe-uk1)²⁷ synthetic dataset (accession [EGAD00001006673](https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001006673)²⁸). The GEUVADIS data can be used as a realistic example dataset to test the WP4 workflows on new compute infrastructures.

Training materials

We have also developed training materials to make it easier for third parties to adopt our workflows. The tutorials for the *cis*-eQTL analysis workflows (1-4) are available on the CINECA WP4 [Github page](https://github.com/CINECA-project/wp4-federated-joint-cohort-analysis/blob/master/4.4-federated-eQTL-analysis/workflow_execution.md)²⁹. The tutorials for the *trans*-eQTL workflows (5-6) are available from the [eQTLGen Phase 2 Cookbook](https://eqtlgen.github.io/eqtlgen-web-site/eQTLGen-p2-cookbook.html)³⁰ page on Github.

Federated analysis use cases

1. Federated *cis*-eQTL analysis to expand the eQTL Catalogue

We have applied the *cis*-QTL workflows (1-4) to two external datasets: (i) lymphoblastoid cell lines (n=528) from the CoLaus cohort hosted at the University of Lausanne, and (ii) stimulated monocytes from the Kim-Hellmuth_2017(19) study hosted at Helmholtz Center Munich. In both cohorts we have used the manual federation strategy outlined on Figure 1.

²² <https://www.cineca-project.eu/cineca-synthetic-datasets>

²³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress/studies/E-MTAB-6666>

²⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress/studies/E-MTAB-6667>

²⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB3366>

²⁶ <https://www.internationalgenome.org/data-portal/data-collection>

²⁷ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/synthetic-data/scd-europe-uk1>

²⁸ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001006673>

²⁹

https://github.com/CINECA-project/wp4-federated-joint-cohort-analysis/blob/master/4.4-federated-eQTL-analysis/workflow_execution.md

³⁰ <https://eqtlgen.github.io/eqtlgen-web-site/eQTLGen-p2-cookbook.html>

For the CoLaus cohort, we started with an existing RNA-seq count matrix and used the eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm workflow to normalise the read counts in a standardised manner. We also used a pre-existing imputed genotype VCF file and performed cis-eQTL analysis using the eQTL-Catalogue/qtldmap workflow. The analysis of individual-level data was performed by Anneke Brümmer at the University of Lausanne. The eQTL summary statistics in standard format were then transferred to the University of Tartu. In parallel, we also performed eQTL analysis on four other lymphoblastoid cell line datasets locally available at the University of Tartu (GEUVADIS (18), GENCORD, TwinsUK and GTEx) using the same workflows 1-4 described above. Finally, we performed inverse variance weighted meta-analysis based on summary statistics from all five dataset. One example association is shown in Table 1. Using uniform data normalisation and analysis workflow has ensured that effect sizes are highly comparable between studies.

Study	Variant	Gene	beta	se	N
GEUVADIS	chr17_35243422_C_A	SLFN5	1.18	0.0323	445
GENCORD	chr17_35243422_C_A	SLFN5	1.17	0.0458	190
GTEx	chr17_35243422_C_A	SLFN5	1.17	0.0457	147
TwinsUK	chr17_35243422_C_A	SLFN5	1.26	0.0295	418
CoLaus	chr17_35243422_C_A	SLFN5	1.27	0.0187	528
Meta-analysis	chr17_35243422_C_A	SLFN5	1.24	0.0130	1789

Table 1. Example association between chr17_35243422_C_A variant and SLFN5 gene. GEUVADIS, GENCORD, GTEx and TwinsUK datasets were analysed locally at the University of Tartu and the CoLaus dataset was analysed locally at the University of Lausanne. CoLaus summary statistics were transferred to University of Tartu where meta-analysis was performed.

For the Kim-Hellmuth_2017 (19) study, we used the eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute workflow to impute genotypes to 1000 Genomes 30x on GRCh38 reference genome. Since the Kim-Hellmuth_2017 study used gene expression microarrays to measure gene expression and only normalised gene expression values were available, we used these existing gene expression values in together with imputed genotypes directly in the eQTL-Catalogue/qtldmap workflow. The analysis of individual-level data was performed by Anshika Chowdhary at the Helmholtz Center Munich and only eQTL summary statistics were transferred to the University of Tartu.

These two use cases highlight the benefits of having modular workflows for different subtasks (gene expression quantification, normalisation, genotype imputation and association testing) that can be mixed and matched depending on the type of data available at different cohorts. They also demonstrate that Nextflow workflows together with Docker/Singularity containers is a robust system to execute complex analytical workflows on diverse compute infrastructures, removing the need to manually install dependencies and keep track of the execution of different workflow steps.

2. Federated trans-eQTL meta-analysis across multiple cohorts.

We have performed a genome-wide *trans*-eQTL mapping analysis in 13 cohorts comprising 6569 samples. These cohorts are subset of the 37 cohorts included in the eQTLGen Consortium (20) Phase 1 analysis and include The Estonian Biobank (IlluminaHT12v3 and RNA-seq sub-cohorts) (21), BIOS (presented by 8 sub-cohorts) (22), Fehrmann (Fehrmann-H8v2 and Fehrmann-HT12v3 subcohorts) (23), and GTEx (release 8) (24), with some comprising of whole genome sequencing data, and others containing array genotyping data. Similarly, both microarray and RNA-seq gene expression data is represented by these 13 cohorts. This was done according to the eQTLGen Phase 2 *trans*-eQTL mapping analysis cookbook described above³¹.

Following this cookbook, for each cohort, we obtained genotype data without variant level quality control already performed (if available), and expression data represented by gene counts. Following quality control, all datasets were converted to human genome build version 38, genotype data was harmonised, and imputed following imputation workflows described before. Using the *trans*-eQTL encoding and meta-analysis workflows, cohorts were analysed and combined. Before the meta-analysis step, we filtered variants to have minor allele frequencies above 1%, minor allele counts above 10, imputation R^2 above 0.4, and HWE p-value above 1×10^{-6} . Four genetic principal components and 20 gene expression principal components were used as covariates. Out of 12 293 683 variants, and 20 034 genes, we found 1 728 110 significant variant-gene-expression combinations (p-value $< 5 \times 10^{-8}$), comprising 14 868 affected genes, and 1 057 638 variants. This translates to 23 068 locus-gene combinations. Figure 6 shows the strongest effect per 2 Mb window for every significantly affected gene.

³¹ <https://eqtlgen.github.io/eqtlgen-web-site/eQTLGen-p2-cookbook.htm>

Figure 6. Dot-plot of genome-wide eQTL meta-analysis results. Strongest effect per 2 Mb window is presented for each eQTL gene and the P-value threshold for significant effect is 5×10^{-8} . Sideplots show a rolling sum of significant variants and genes in each 2 megabase window.

3.3 Discussion and next steps

Within this deliverable, we have achieved three main objectives. First, we have created a set of six modular and containerised computational workflows to support federated analysis splicing and gene expression QTLs. Secondly, we have set up two realistic open access datasets to support further development, testing and deployment of these workflows on various compute infrastructures. Finally, we have demonstrated the utility of these workflows in two realistic federated analysis settings. In the last six months of the project, we will continue working towards demonstrating end-to-end federated analysis. Specifically, this will involve setting up three open access eQTL cohorts (two described above + one more), harmonising metadata between these cohorts (CINECA WP3), making these cohorts discoverable via three separate Beacon instances hosted in Europe, Canada and Africa (CINECA WP1), and providing access to individual-level data from these cohorts via authorisation and authentication infrastructure (CINECA WP2).

We also see that in addition to simplifying development and testing of federated analysis workflows, the synthetic and open access datasets also have a great potential to improve federated analysis

interoperability between cohorts when providing access to individual-level real data is either impractical or impossible. In this framework, cohorts can set up ‘synthetic twins’ of their real genomic datasets that can be made available either publicly or via a separate workspace in their private TRE. These synthetic datasets can then be used to develop data analysis logic and test deployment infrastructure on the cohort-specific TRE. Once the workflow executes successfully, it can then be transferred to another workspace where a local analyst from the cohort (see Figure 1) will execute the workflow on private individual-level data. Instead of different cohorts generating their own synthetic data from scratch, they can re-use existing open access datasets that match their use cases as closely as possible. For example, if the cohort needs a synthetic RNA-seq dataset, they could re-use the data from the GEUVADIS project mentioned above. If they need a raw or imputed genotyping microarray data, they could re-use the CEDAR datasets that we have prepared here. This can greatly reduce the effort needed to set up ‘synthetic twins’ while ensuring that the data behaves as closely as possible to real data in the analysis.

We believe that the six workflows that we have developed here are a significant improvement above the previously available state-of-the-art. The original eQTL analysis cookbook³² relied on manual installation of software dependencies, required manual execution of each analysis step, and implemented only a subset of the analyses presented here. Similarly, prior to the genotype imputation workflow that we have developed here, the easiest way to impute genotypes was to use the Michigan Imputation Server (12), but this required uploading individual-level genotype data to a server based in the United States. Our choice of the Nextflow language and the Docker/Singularity containerisation framework is consistent with other community efforts (such as nf-core (25)) to make reproducible and well-maintained workflows available for easy deployment on various compute infrastructures. These technological advances are essential to enable federated analysis of human genetic datasets made accessible via various Trusted Research Environments hosted on diverse cloud environments.

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5. Abbreviations

QTL - quantitative trait locus, a genetic variant associated with one or more (molecular) trait

TRE - trusted research environment

SNP - single nucleotide polymorphism

GA4GH - Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

VCF - variant call format

PCA - principal component analysis

MDS - multidimensional scaling

6. Delivery and schedule

Delivered on time.

7. Adjustments made

None.

8. Appendices

Appendix 1

